

D7.2 Communications & Outreach Plan (COP) 2.0

WP7 Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation

July 2025

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LandSeaLot has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme for Research and Innovation under grant agreement No 101134575. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. UK participants in Horizon Europe Project LandSeaLot are supported by UKRI grant numbers: 10109592 University of Stirling and 10107554 Plymouth Marine Laboratory.

Title	D7.2 - Communications & Outreach Plan (COP) 2.0
Work Package	WP7
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Due Date	31.07.2025
Submission Date	17.07.2025
Version	2.0

Dissemination Level

- PU: Public
- PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission)
- RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission)
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LandSeaLot: Land-Sea interface: Let’s observe together! is a Research and Innovation action (RIA) funded by the Horizon Europe Work programme topics addressed: HORIZON-CL6-2023-01-11: Reducing observation gaps in the land-sea interface area. Start date: 01 February 2024. End date: 31 January 2028.

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List of Referenced Acronyms and Terms

Table 1. List of referenced acronyms and terms

Acronym	Description	Acronym	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence	ICOS-ERIC	Integrated Carbon Observing System European Research Infrastructure Consortium
Chl-a	Chlorophyll-a	JERICO-RI	European Research Infrastructure for Coastal Observation
Copernicus	EU Earth Observation Programme	KPI	Key Performance Indicator
DANUBIUS-RI	International Centre for Advanced Studies on River-Sea Systems Research Infrastructure	HELCOM	Baltic Marine Environment Protection Commission
DestinE	Destination Earth	INSPIRE	Infrastructure for Spatial Information in Europe
DG DEFIS	European Commission Directorate General for Defense Industry & Space	LCD	LandSeaLot Co-Designer forum
DG ENV	European Commission Directorate General for the Environment	LCE	LandSeaLot Citizen Empowerment Forum
DG MARE	European Commission Directorate General for Maritime Affairs & Fisheries	LCOS	LandSeaLot Common Observation Strategy for the land-sea interface area
DMP	Data Management Plan	LIL	LandSeaLot Integration Lab
DTO	Digital Twin Ocean	LSC	LandSeaLot Science Community Forum
EEA	European Environment Agency	LSI	Land-Sea Interface
E.I.	Expected Impact	LSL	LandSeaLot
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network	MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
ENVRI - board	Board of European Environmental Research Infrastructures	NN	Neural Network
EO	Earth Observation	OSPAR	Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic
E.O.	Expected Outcome	SeaDataNet	Pan-European infrastructure to ease the access to marine data
EOOS	European Ocean Observing System	SG	Stakeholder Group

ESA	European Space Agency	SotA	State-of-the-Art
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable	SSL	Sea Surface Level
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation	SST	Sea Surface Temperature
GEOS	Global Earth Observation System of Systems	TSM	Total Suspended Matter
GOOS	Global Ocean Observing System	WFD	Water Framework Directive

I. About LandSeaLot and this document

The purpose of this document is to describe, formally update and reissue the **Communication and Outreach Plan (COP)** of the **LandSeaLot** project. It lays out the different target recipients, stakeholders, methodologies, tools, channels, materials and activities that will be leveraged to support the delivery of the aim, objectives and expected outcomes of LandSeaLot, as described in the sections below. **All updates in this document are preceded by “Version 2.0 Update”.**

This is a living document that will be updated periodically by the Work Package 7 team; it is now officially delivered as Version 2.0 to meet D7.2 (M18) of the project.

The Communication and Outreach activities of the LandSeaLot Consortium and Work Package 7 are detailed and assessed throughout this document. An overview of communication and dissemination outputs, many of which are being continually updated, is provided on the following page (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Work Package 7 ongoing outputs

Overall aim of the LandSeaLot project

The **LandSeaLot** (“**Land-Sea** interface: **Let’s observe together!**”) project is a four-year research and innovation action seeking to integrate, scale-up and enhance existing observation efforts, conducted by satellites or *in situ* (including by citizen scientists), together with numerical simulations, to better study the land-sea interface area. Funded by the European Union (EU)’s Horizon Europe Framework Programme for Research and Innovation and the UK Research and Innovation Agency, it comprises 20 partners and 3 associated partners spanning 12 European nations.

The overall aim of LandSeaLot is to bring together interdisciplinary expertise to co-design a **common observation strategy** for the land-sea interface (the LandSeaLot Common Observation Strategy - LCOS), where terrestrial and marine habitats meet. This will be achieved through better integration and collaboration across scientific domains, Research Infrastructures (RIs), expert communities, and key stakeholders, and through the expansion of the *in situ* observation capacity, including the use of cost-effective observation technology, such as specific, low-cost, reliable sensors to be used via citizen science engagement. The resulting observational data and integrated information products will be made accessible through existing European data services, namely the European Marine Observation Data Network (EMODnet) and Copernicus, and for exploitation via the European Digital Twin Ocean. The project will bring novel approaches to help achieve the goals of the EU Water and Marine Strategy Framework Directives (WFD and MSFD, respectively), as well as the EU Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030” and the wider objectives of the European Green Deal, thereby also contributing to the United Nations (UN) Agenda 2030 and its Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Objectives and expected outcomes of LandSeaLot

LandSeaLot will develop and test a framework for observing the land-sea interface area through the objectives below. Specific communication and outreach outputs have and are continually being planned to communicate, promote and support the project objectives and their achievement, as reflected in the editorial plans presented in Section IV.

- Defragment LSI communities and improve governance for observation of the LSI by joining four scientific observation communities (*in situ*, satellite, modelling and citizen science), at least three Ris (DANUBIUS, JERICO, ICOS), two key European stakeholders (ESA, EEA), and three Copernicus services (Marine, Land, Climate) and co-designing a Common Observation Strategy.
- Enhance data interoperability across aquatic domains and observing communities by the development of interoperability standards supporting the harmonisation between *in situ* and satellite observations and citizen science data.
- Expand observation capacity through citizen science and low-cost sensors deployment, by: 1) assessing the potential of emerging low-cost technologies to reduce observation gaps in space and time; 2) empowering citizens in contributing to environmental science at the LSI, and 3) developing data management solutions for these emerging data streams (low-

cost technologies, citizen science observations), by creating FAIR citizen data flows to EMODnet and contributing to international best practices.

- Develop methods to fill data gaps in the LSI across domains and observation communities (*in situ*, satellite, modelling and citizen science), through identification of data gaps and testing potential solutions to fill these gaps, including common observation protocols, multi-sensor satellite products and model approaches.
- Improve modelling and forecasting capacity in support of digital twin development of the LSI, by developing: 1) fit-to-purpose observation-based integrated products supporting calibration, and a range of models, and 2) tools for better integration of model outputs with satellite data and *in situ* observations.
- Ensure the LandSeaLot legacy and its long-term impact by: 1) developing mechanisms to ensure long-lasting commitments of the communities involved in the implementation of the Common Observation Strategy, and 2) involving organisations involved in development of data aggregators and interoperability standards
- Promote the European know-how and leadership on LSI observation by sharing our strategies, data interoperability standards and lessons learnt through policy briefs and training sessions and engaging with European and global initiatives and networks.

The expected project **outcomes** include:

- **[+More Observations] Increased availability of integrated *in situ* observations at the land-sea interface area, with particular emphasis on river mouths, estuaries and deltas in Europe.** Following aligned data standards and best practices, LandSeaLot will advance the interoperability of essential variables presently measured by different RIs and through different protocols, thereby enabling the joint use of these data. LandSeaLot will develop interoperability solutions and FAIR data flow for i.e., river load and discharge data, and for the new observational data streams obtained with low-cost observation techniques and via citizen science. Integrated observations will be piloted in the context of the assessment of:
 - Better understanding of lateral carbon fluxes and marine carbon stocks.
 - Enhanced prediction of emerging threats caused by climate change, towards informing optimal adaptation strategies and measures by communities living in the land-sea interface area, e.g., floods, sea level rise.
 - Biodiversity preservation strategies, including by predicting and mitigating the spread of pollution.

All *in situ* observations will be made available through existing aggregators e.g., SeaDataNet and EU data services, i.e., EMODnet and Copernicus Marine service ‘In Situ TAC’, that feed into EDITO and the European DTO, and INSPIRE. The DANUBIUS Data Centre will be connected to EMODnet.

- **[+Better Models] Improved hydrological, biogeochemical, ecological and coastal modelling based on the integration of new sources of *in situ* observations, remote sensing data and their combination at the land-sea interface area.** LandSeaLot will explore and pilot options to:
 - Better integrate new sources of observations (*in situ*, citizen science and low-cost sensor and satellite) in models, either as model input or as improved model validation data.
 - Address modelling challenges that are specific to the land-sea interface area, such as presence of intertidal areas, increase of spatial resolution, or increase of spatial-temporal gradients, and develop a roadmap for further model improvement in the land-sea interface area.
 - Develop a strategy to estimate land-based inputs of carbon, nutrients and plastics as adequate model input to coastal model applications throughout Europe, including Copernicus models. A strategy will be piloted for making observations and (model) estimates of land-based inputs FAIR at a European scale.

The resulting model improvements and strategies will be tested to address local societal challenges in nine pilot areas - i.e., the “**LandSeaLot Integration Labs**” (LILs)- towards informing the **LandSeaLot Common Observation Strategy**, while promoting European modelling know-how, leadership and capacity in support of digital twinning efforts in the land-sea interface area.

- **[+Connected Communities] Enhanced networking between relevant observation communities (*in situ*, airborne, satellite, citizen science, etc.) and training of the citizen science community in the approach to the observation of the land-sea interface area, making use of newly developed low-cost technology.** LandSeaLot will establish cross-community fora to foster networking between observation communities: *in situ*, airborne, satellite and citizen science. By working at both strategic, methodological and implementation levels, LandSeaLot will remove barriers between research communities (e.g., river, marine, physics, chemistry, biology); land and marine (including hydrology) Earth Observation (EO) communities; *in situ* and satellite communities (e.g., ESA Ocean Science Cluster activities); and observation and modelling communities working on applications close to shore. By the end of the project, members of these fora will constitute a **Community of Practice**, promoting the value of this cross-community approach for observing the land-sea interface area.

[+Fit-for-purpose Decision Support Products] Strengthened collaboration and improved governance for the observation of the land-sea interface area, leading to better, fit-for-purpose advanced data products in support of decision-making.

Advanced products will be developed from: 1) integration of *in situ* multi-source data, as improved input data to models; 2) the merging of different satellite data, removing observation discontinuities in the land-sea continuum, and harmonising multi-scale observation strategies across observation disciplines (e.g., altimetry and radiometry); and

3) the joint exploitation of observations and model outputs, for reducing the overall uncertainty, thereby maximising its impact on robust decision-making. The advanced products will be piloted in LILs via different applications.

LandSeaLot Key Exploitable Results

Version 2.0 Update: Identified in D7.5, the LandSeaLot Initial Exploitation Plan 1.0, LandSeaLot will deliver twelve Key Exploitable Results (KERs) pertaining to the five Exploitation targets (Governance & Communities of Practice, Best Practices and innovative strategies for observation, Best Practices for Data Management, Market-Driven Solutions, and Policy). These KERs will be developed during the project and exploited during and beyond the project’s lifetime. Initial plans to develop and exploit LandSeaLot KERs beyond the project’s lifetime are included in Section VII, Post-Project Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation.

Table 2. LandSeaLot KERs

Governance & Communities of Practice	Best Practices & Innovative Strategies for Observation	Best Practices for Data Management	Market-Driven Solutions	Policy
KER 1.1 – LCOS & Agreements by parties	KER 2.1 – Best practices for integrating observations and models at the LSI	KER 3.1 Interoperability solutions for river and estuarine data	KER 4.1 – Catalogue of low-cost technologies	KER 5.1 - Policy Brief
KER 1.2 – Gap analysis & effective implementation of LCOS in LILs	KER 2.2 – Improved observations of key LSI processes and variables	KER 3.2 – Interoperability solutions for citizen science and low-cost sensor data	KER 4.2 – Extended portfolio of EO products	
KER 1.3 – Citizen Science Hub	KER 2.3 – Toolkit for deployment of citizen science via European marinas		KER 4.3 – Generic data & Visualisation services and apps	

For updated Communication and Dissemination activities and outputs that will support Exploitation targets and KERs, see Section IV: Planning of Communication & Outreach Activities in this document.

II: Communication and Outreach Strategy

WHY: General communication and outreach objectives

The **LandSeaLot Communication and Outreach strategy** is geared at supporting the successful delivery of the project objectives and its results, towards generating its expected outcomes, legacy and long-term impact. Specific Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for communication and other project outputs are laid out in Section V: Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). The **general communication** and **outreach objectives** are as follows:

- To raise **awareness** of the LandSeaLot project amongst key stakeholders (selected target audiences), generating interest for the project and attracting key stakeholder communities to create the conditions for a strong engagement and participation in planned activities.
- To **promote interactions** with **key stakeholders** and **communities** to actively invite their participation, input and feedback in the co-design, testing, and pilot implementation of proposed strategies and methods.
- To **demonstrate the value** of integrated observations to address societal challenges faced by local communities and beyond at the land-sea interface.
- To **cultivate support** from key stakeholders towards the future establishment of a long-term collaboration framework enabling the implementation of the **LandSeaLot Common Observation Strategy** for the land-sea interface area.
- Connecting to policymakers and wider society to enhance the **impact** of the project.

WHO: Target recipients for LandSeaLot communications

Considering the overall aim of LandSeaLot, **11** groups have been identified as essential recipients for communication, dissemination and exploitation activities that will be designed, planned and rolled out throughout the project. These groups constitute LandSeaLot’s audience but are also active stakeholders who are well positioned to engage with, participate in and/or benefit from the project. They are therefore referred to as Stakeholder **Groups** (SGs). These SGs are described in Table 3 below.

Table 3. LandSeaLot Stakeholder Groups (SGs)

LandSeaLot Stakeholder Groups (SGs)	
SG1	Researchers and data scientists and managers Scientists (<i>in situ</i> /satellite observation, modelling, research) bridging land-sea interface area communities, including data scientists. Data managers working in marine and freshwater domains.
SG2	Research Infrastructures The LandSeaLot RI partners (JERICO-RI, DANUBIUS-RI, ICOS-ERIC), other relevant environmental RIs (eLTER, EMBRC, Lifewatch, EPOS), and the ENVRI Board.

SG3	Long-term EU marine data services and relevant EU initiatives Copernicus Marine, EMODnet, SEADaNet, EuroGOOS
SG4	Users and managers of the land-sea environment Delta and estuaries management organisations, (Marine) Protected Area managers, Port Authorities, fishermen and aquaculture professionals, agricultural communities in delta areas affected by saltwater intrusion and reduction of freshwater availability (e.g., farmers), communities affected by the loss of land (e.g., coastal tourism destination management organisations and operators, inhabitants of urban areas exposed to extreme events) and local NGOs
SG5	Citizen science leaders and multipliers Citizen scientists, citizen science networks and organisations, marinas, teachers and trainers
SG6	Innovators (SMEs) Producers and/or distributors of low-cost remote sensors and technologies
SG7	Mission Lighthouses and Blue Parks initiatives: Coordination & Support Actions supporting Mission Lighthouses and Blue Parks initiatives
SG8	Water quality reporting organisations: EEA, Regional Sea Conventions (i.e., OSPAR, HELCOM, Black Sea Commission, Barcelona Convention), national Member States reporting to MSFD & WFD
SG9	European Space Agency (ESA)
SG10	EU and international policy and governance bodies European Commission (DG ENV, DG MARE, DG DEFIS), International Ocean Commission
SG11	International ocean observing efforts and UN Agenda 2030 initiatives GEOSS, UN Decade of Ocean Science and UN Decade of Ecosystem Restoration

The **stakeholder engagement strategy** has been embedded in the project since its inception, being articulated around ensuring proper engagement of key actors at **strategic, methodological, and implementation** levels. With this in mind, LandSeaLot established **three distinctive cross-community fora** as means of promoting and enabling interactions across specific SGs:

- The **LandSeaLot Science Committee Forum (LSC)** aims to close gaps between scientific communities and domains, leveraging the expertise of Team members engaged in the project Consortium (SG1). It will foster mutual understanding (common ontology), harmonisation and the emergence of a common vision, and strategy for observing the land-sea interface area. Through the LSC the scientific perspective on how to improve the observation of the land-sea interface area is assessed: What is the scientific state-of-the-art in this field and how can it be advanced? Specific Terms of Reference have been laid out to guide the activity and functioning of the Forum, defining its objectives, modus operandi, timing, and composition.
- The **LandSeaLot Co-Designer Forum (LCD)** brings together representatives of key stakeholders of the land-sea observation and users of such observations (SG2, SG3, SG8, SG9, SG10, SG11), as well as connecting with SG4 via LandSeaLot Integration

Labs. It will co-design the LandSeaLot Common Observation Strategy for the land-sea interface area through planned, targeted interactions, supported by gap analyses, methodologies and recommendations stemming from the LandSeaLot Science Committee Forum.

- **Version 2.0 Update:** The **LandSeaLot Citizen Science Hub** (formerly the LandSeaLot Citizen Empowerment Forum) brings together LandSeaLot researchers, citizen scientist groups, local communities, and other civil bodies including marinas, to develop ideas and initiatives that build capacity among citizens to observe the land-sea interface area. These ideas and initiatives will be documented on the [Citizen Science Hub section of the LandSeaLot website](#), which will be regularly updated with events, training opportunities, case studies and success stories, with a strong focus on how the LandSeaLot Integration Labs (LILs) are collaborating with and onboarding different actors in local communities in the land-sea environment. The Hub will be instrumental for piloting a range of innovative methods, technologies, products and strategies deployed by the project, and for connecting the European citizen science community.

Version 2.0 Update: the visualisation of Forums and Stakeholder Groups has been updated into an interactive infographic, which is included on the LandSeaLot website to introduce the [Community Engagement section](#) (see Figure 2).

Based on the Stakeholder Groups mapped as relevant for LandSeaLot (Table 3), the project Consortium maintains a comprehensive internal **stakeholder database** that is continuously updated, streamlined and leveraged to activate and manage stakeholder interactions, observing all applicable, legal data privacy requirements and obligations including GDPR.

Communication and outreach requirements to support engagement with target stakeholder groups across all LandSeaLot Fora and LandSeaLot Integration Labs are continuously gathered via ongoing interaction with the project Consortium and project collaborators such as marinas and citizen science groups.

Figure 2. LandSeaLot Fora and target stakeholder groups

WHAT: Key messages

The following general, core messages are used to structure and articulate communications regarding LandSeaLot.

On LandSeaLot's aim:

- **Version 2.0 Update: Project summary for all audiences:** LandSeaLot is a Horizon Europe project that seeks to integrate and enhance existing coastal observation efforts - including *in situ*, satellite, modelling and citizen science - to better study the land-sea interface area, where terrestrial and marine habitats meet.
- **Project summary for specialised audiences:** LandSeaLot brings together interdisciplinary expertise to co-design a Common Observation Strategy for the land-sea interface area. This will be achieved through better integration and collaboration across scientific domains, Research Infrastructures (RIs), expert communities, and key stakeholders, and through the expansion of the *in situ* observation capacity, including by using cost-effective observation technology, such as specific, low-cost, reliable sensors to be used via citizen science engagement. The resulting observational data and integrated information products will be made accessible through existing European data services, such as EMODnet and Copernicus, including for exploitation via the European Digital Twin Ocean. The project will bring novel approaches to help monitor progress towards achievement of the goals of the EU Water and Marine Strategy Framework Directives, as well as the EU Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030”, in support of the wider objectives of the European Ocean Pact and the European Green Deal.
- **Project information:** LandSeaLot is a four year, 20-partner and 3 associated partners consortium, EU and UK funded, research and innovation action that will connect fragmented research communities and scientific domains to achieve an integrated, cost-effective and robust observation strategy for the land-sea interface area. The project is geared at contributing to achieving the goals of the EU Water Framework Directive, the EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive, the EU Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030” and the wider objectives of the European Green Deal, thereby also contributing to the United Nations Agenda 2030 and its Sustainable Development Goals.

On LandSeaLot ambition & overarching outcomes:

- **LandSeaLot will deliver a Common Observation Strategy for the land-sea interface area, with a focus on river mouths, estuaries and deltas in Europe:** LandSeaLot brings together and builds observation capacity among leading scientific expertise, European land-sea observing capabilities, research infrastructures, data services, and local stakeholders, including citizen science groups, to establish better integration and collaboration between and across communities working in the land-sea interface area. Together with these communities, the project will co-design the LandSeaLot Common Observation Strategy for the land-sea interface area. This strategy will be piloted in nine

LandSeaLot Integration Labs and communicated to relevant European and international stakeholders, for future adoption and implementation.

- **LandSeaLot will result in strengthened collaboration and improved governance in observing the land-sea interface area:** By bridging scientific observation communities (*in situ*, satellite, modelling and citizen science), key Research Infrastructures (such as DANUBIUS, JERICO, ICOS), European agencies (ESA, EEA), and Copernicus (Marine, Land, and Climate) services, LandSeaLot will pave the way for improved governance of European observing capabilities at the land-sea interface area.
- **This improved governance will lead to better, fit-for-purpose advanced data products in support of decision-makers:** LandSeaLot will enhance the quantity and quality of the river and coastal multidisciplinary observational data that is made available to achieve EU policy objectives i.e., WFD, MSFD, and the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030, and to deliver input into European and global environmental indicators. New methods and tools will be deployed to ensure that new and better data, increased in **F**indability, **A**ccessibility, **I**nteroperability, and **R**eproducibility (FAIRness), can be leveraged to develop more accurate, advanced data products that inform decision making on environmental, economic, and social processes and activities taking place at the land-sea interface area.
- **LandSeaLot will engage with local communities to align scientific efforts with societal needs and expectations:** The LandSeaLot Integration Labs will support the LandSeaLot mission to develop an observation strategy along the land-sea interface areas as testing centres designed to pilot the proposed methodologies, tools and improvements emerging from the project, informing a user and community-based observation strategy across local regions. It will demonstrate how increased observation capabilities and innovative integrative methodologies provide essential knowledge to address societal challenges, such as reducing **marine pollution** from land, ensuring **biodiversity** protection or adapting to **climate change** threats.
- **LandSeaLot will scale up the European (land, marine and freshwater) environmental knowledge value chain in support of digital twinning efforts:** LandSeaLot will provide new interoperable and integrated datasets that address the needs and/or interests of a range of stakeholders, including the European Space Agency (ESA); the European Environmental Agency (EEA); national monitoring programmes; key European data services i.e., Copernicus Land, Climate and Marine services and EMODnet; EuroGOOS and the Global Earth Observation System of Systems (GEOSS). These datasets will foster the further development of a more robust European environmental modelling framework for exploring “*What-If?*” scenarios, contributing to European efforts to build a digital twin of the Earth (DestinE) and the European Digital Twin Ocean (DTO).

In addition, key messages tailored to **specific target audiences** are outlined in Table 4.

Table 4. Key messages for each Stakeholder Group

Topic	Target Stakeholder Group	Engagement Level
SG1		
Researchers, data scientists, and data managers		
Connecting data scientists working with EO data, <i>in situ</i> data, and modellers	Let's Observe Together! LandSeaLot will bring together data scientists, researchers and specialists from modelling, <i>in situ</i> and Earth Observation communities working in the land-sea interface area, proposing new approaches to harmonise observing methodologies and to integrate the different sources of data, towards streamlining the generation of new, integrated data and data products.	Awareness
Data, models, standards	LandSeaLot will make an inventory of model inputs and outputs for common modelling approaches and link these to potential sources of yet unexploited observation data from satellites, <i>in situ</i> observations and citizen science and low-cost sensor data to streamline the generation of integrated data.	Awareness
LandSeaLot Fora	LandSeaLot will reduce gaps and inconsistencies existing in available <i>in situ</i> observations, identifying areas where they overlap and/or are insufficient. By engaging with LandSeaLot Fora, you can stay informed of the latest scientific developments, while contributing to further shaping them.	Engagement and uptake of resulting methods
LandSeaLot (future) Community of Practice	LandSeaLot will create new, innovative and strategic collaborative frameworks for communities involved in observation, provision of data and information, and knowledge building at the land-sea interface area. By engaging with LandSeaLot you can contribute to shaping these efforts, including the Community of Practice that will sustain a cross-community approach for observing the land-sea interface.	Engagement and uptake of resulting methods
SG2		
Research Infrastructures: (JERICO-RI, DANUBIUS-RI, ICOS-ERIC) environmental RIs (eLTER, EMBRC, Lifewatch, AQUACOSM) and the ENVRI/BeeRI		
LandSeaLot Co-design Forum	Let's Observe Together! LandSeaLot is bringing research infrastructures together to enhance the observation of the land-sea interface area. JERICO-RI, DANUBIUS, ICOS-ERIC and other RIs will be teaming up to harmonise observing methodologies, enabling the integration of different sources of data, including from citizen science.	Engagement

Aligned methods across Research Infrastructures	LandSeaLot will assess the differences in protocols between different observation communities (such as DANUBIUS-RI, JERICO-RI, ICOS-ERIC) and propose methods to deal with inconsistencies.	Awareness
Demonstrating the added value of research infrastructures	LandSeaLot will empower existing Research Infrastructures to jointly provide European decision makers with the necessary data products and knowledge they need to better manage the land-sea interface area, with a focus on river mouths, estuaries and deltas in Europe. This will enhance the visibility of RIs' contribution to delivering the objectives of the WFD, MSFD, and EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030".	Engagement and uptake of common observation strategy
SG3	Long-term EU marine data services and relevant EU initiatives: Copernicus, EMODnet, SeaDataNet, EuroGOOS	
Enhancing European assets	LandSeaLot will generate new observational, FAIR data and integrated information products on the land-sea interface area for assimilation into EMODnet and Copernicus services. By linking <i>in situ</i> observations and citizen science with satellite observations and models, it will contribute to better, fit-for-purpose data products and to build more accurate " What if " scenarios into DestinE and the European Digital Twin Ocean.	Engagement and uptake of resulting data
Enhancing European assets	LandSeaLot will develop new tools and processes to ensure that new data captured via innovative methods (cost-effective sensors, citizen science) feed into European aggregators (i.e., Copernicus, EMODnet), so that it is made FAIR for wider usage, contributing to better study the land-sea interface area.	Engagement and uptake of resulting methods
LandSeaLot Co-Designer Forum	LandSeaLot will actively engage with representatives of EU data services and initiatives to discuss how the project's activities can deliver value to their users. These consultations will be part of the LandSeaLot Co-Designer Forum, in which EU marine data services and initiatives are encouraged to participate.	Engagement and uptake of common observation strategy
SG4	Users and managers of the land-sea environment	
LandSeaLot Citizen Science Hub	Let's Observe Together! Your local area has been chosen to host a LandSeaLot Integration Lab: A forum where scientists, public agencies, local governments, businesses, associations, and citizens will come together to pilot innovative ways of observing river mouths, estuaries and deltas in Europe to address local environmental challenges and opportunities. By	Awareness

	participating, you will ensure that European Earth Observation capabilities are shaped to service your needs.	
Local environmental agencies: Join Citizen Science Hub <i>Mitigating threats from climate change</i>	Let's Observe Together! LandSeaLot seeks to improve the availability of timely knowledge to better understand climate change threats to the human and economic activities that take place in river mouths, estuaries and deltas in Europe. By participating in LandSeaLot's Integration Labs and Citizen Empowerment Forum you can contribute to shape scientific efforts to deliver to your monitoring needs.	Engagement
Local associations: Join Citizen Science Hub <i>Reducing plastic pollution, protecting nature and biodiversity</i>	Let's Observe Together! LandSeaLot seeks to improve the availability of scientific knowledge to better preserve biodiversity and human health, reducing pollution coming from land into the sea via river mouths, estuaries and deltas in Europe. A better understanding of the plastic transport pathways will inform the design of better measures to decrease pollution. By participating in LandSeaLot Integration Labs and the Citizen Science Hub you can contribute to local efforts to protect nature in your area, but also in other European regions.	Engagement
Local Businesses: Join Citizen Science Hub <i>Mitigating risks and improving operations</i>	Let's Observe Together! Join LandSeaLot Citizen Empowerment Forum to inform the development of better Earth Observation data products that support your economic activity, helping you to anticipate risks from climate change and/or tap into operational opportunities to improve your business results.	Engagement
SG5	Citizen science leaders & multipliers	
LandSeaLot Citizen Science Hub	Let's Observe Together! Are you associated with a citizen science group? Join the LandSeaLot Citizen Science Hub and team up with researchers to better study rivers, estuaries, and deltas in Europe, using innovative sensors and technology. LandSeaLot will gear you up with skills and tools to activate your group and make a difference in your local area.	Awareness and engagement
Citizen Science Hub	Let's Observe Together! LandSeaLot is offering training opportunities to citizen science groups that wish to engage in the observation of the land-sea interface area, where terrestrial and marine habitats meet. Join us in delivering the knowledge we need to Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030!	Awareness and engagement
SG6	Innovators: Suppliers of low-cost remote sensors and technologies	

Offer your technology to new communities	Let's Observe Together! LandSeaLot aims to create synergy between cost-effective technology producers and information users, catalysing market opportunities and facilitating widespread adoption.	Awareness
Offer your technology to citizen science	Let's Observe Together! Cost-effective technologies provide citizen science groups with an affordable solution to contribute to the observation of the land-sea interface area, where terrestrial and marine habitats meet.	Awareness
LandSeaLot procurement opportunities	Let's Observe Together! LandSeaLot is looking to buy your cost-effective marine technology! We aim to procure €250,000 of marine technologies to scale solutions that meet ocean management and decision-making needs. We are looking for tools, devices or systems designed, developed and priced to be affordable and accessible to a wide range of users.	Engagement
SG7	Mission Lighthouses & Blue Parks initiatives	
Citizen science opportunities	Let's Observe Together! LandSeaLot is bringing scientists, local governments and agencies, businesses, associations and citizens together to enhance the observation of river mouths, estuaries and deltas in Europe. This will lead to better data products and " what if " scenarios in support of meeting the goals of the EU Mission "Restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2030". You can team up with LandSeaLot to contribute and benefit from these efforts and empower citizen scientists engaged in your Mission Lighthouse or related Blue Park initiatives with new methods, skills and innovative tools!	Awareness
LandSeaLot Fora	Let's Observe Together! LandSeaLot will provide a new collaborative framework to support integrated observations of coastal areas, river mouths, estuaries and deltas in Europe, which will be relevant for the delivery of the goals of the EU Mission "Restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2030". By engaging with LandSeaLot, you can stay informed of the latest scientific and community developments and convey them to researchers and institutions that are engaged in your Mission Lighthouse or related Blue Park initiatives.	Engagement and uptake of the LCOS for the land-sea interface area
SG8	Water quality reporting organisations	

<p>LandSeaLot value to water quality reporting organisations</p>	<p>LandSeaLot is bringing together interdisciplinary expertise to co-design a Common Observation Strategy for the land-sea interface area. This will be achieved through better integration and collaboration across scientific domains, research infrastructures (RIs), expert communities and key stakeholders, and through the expansion of the <i>in situ</i> observation capacity, including low-cost, reliable sensors to be used predominately via citizen science engagement. The resulting observational data and integrated information products will be made accessible through existing European data services, such as EMODnet and Copernicus, and for exploitation via the European Digital Twin Ocean. The project will bring novel approaches to help monitor progress towards the goals of the EU Water and Marine Strategy Framework Directives, as well as the EU Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030”, in support of the wider objectives of the European Green Deal.</p>	<p>Awareness</p>
<p>LandSeaLot Co-Designer Forum</p>	<p>LandSeaLot will actively engage with representatives of the European Environment Agency, Regional Sea Conventions, and other water quality reporting organisations to discuss what type of data and data products on the land-sea interface area they require to fulfil their monitoring and reporting requirements. These consultations will be part of the LandSeaLot Co-Designer Forum, in which water quality reporting organisations are encouraged to participate.</p>	<p>Engagement</p>
<p>SG9</p>	<p>European Space Agency (ESA)</p>	
<p>LandSeaLot value to Earth Observation</p>	<p>LandSeaLot is bringing together interdisciplinary expertise to co-design a Common Observation Strategy for the land-sea interface area. This will be achieved through better integration and collaboration across scientific domains, research infrastructures (RIs), expert communities, and key stakeholders, and through the expansion of the <i>in situ</i> observation capacity, including by using cost-effective observation technology, such as specific, low-cost, reliable sensors to be used via citizen science engagement. The resulting observational data and integrated information products will be made accessible through existing European data services, such as EMODnet and Copernicus, and for exploitation via the European Digital Twin Ocean.</p>	<p>Awareness</p>

LandSeaLot value to Earth Observation	LandSeaLot will evaluate the added value of multi-sensor satellite products, also combined with models, providing a roadmap for future developments to raise the observation capability across the land sea-interface. It will develop multi-sensor satellite products, calibrated and validated for sea surface temperature (SST), sea surface level (SSL), total suspended matter (TSM), chlorophyll-a (Chl-a) and phytoplankton functional types (PFT).	Awareness
LandSeaLot Co-Designer Forum	LandSeaLot is seeking to actively engage with representatives of ESA to discuss how the project’s activities can deliver value to their users. These consultations will be part of the LandSeaLot Co-Designer Forum, in which ESA will have a key voice amongst relevant European agencies, services and initiatives.	Engagement
Contributing to DestinE and the European Digital Twin Ocean	LandSeaLot will provide new interoperable and integrated datasets which address the needs of a range of stakeholders, including the European Space Agency (ESA). These datasets will foster the further development of a European environmental modelling framework for exploring robust “ What-If? ” scenarios, in support of Destination-Earth and the European Digital Twin Ocean.	Engagement and uptake of common observation strategy
SG10	International policy and governance bodies	
LandSeaLot value to international policy and governance bodies	LandSeaLot is bringing together scientists, European research infrastructures, Earth Observation and data management services, and local stakeholders to pilot innovative ways of observing river mouths, estuaries and deltas. By developing a Common Observation Strategy for the land-sea interface area, it will contribute to provide European and international policy makers with the necessary data products and science-based information they need to address global environmental challenges and meet environmental policy objectives.	Awareness
SG11	International ocean observing efforts and UN Agenda 2030 initiatives	
LandSeaLot value to international ocean observing efforts	LandSeaLot will generate new observational, FAIR data and integrated information products on the land-sea interface area for assimilation into EMODnet and Copernicus services, which contribute to global ocean observing efforts, i.e., GEOSS and relevant initiatives led by the Intergovernmental Ocean Commission (IOC), including GOOS.	Awareness

<p>LandSeaLot value to the UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development</p>	<p>LandSeaLot will provide new interoperable and integrated datasets which address the needs of a range of stakeholders. These datasets will foster the further development of a European environmental modelling framework for exploring robust “What-If?” scenarios, in support of the European Digital Twin Ocean and international digital twinning efforts (i.e., DITTO), contributing towards Goal #8 of the UN Ocean Decade “Delivering a Digital Replica of the Ocean”.</p>	<p>Awareness</p>
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Finally, LandSeaLot will leverage the **expressions of interest** received during its conception as valuable stakeholder testimonials for storytelling and reference:

- “We look forward to the output of LandSeaLot in terms of improved process understanding, monitoring and prediction capabilities for a wide range of phenomena impacting coastal populations.” (ESA)
- “We would welcome the possibility to collaborate with actions to close this important knowledge gap.” (European Commission's Joint Research Centre-Soil Observatory)
- “We can provide recommendations on how to reduce the observation gaps in the land-sea interface area to build a fit-for-purpose European Ocean Observation System.” (EuroGOOS)
- “Observations within LandSeaLot would certainly enable us to concentrate on assessments rather than handling information.” (OSPAR and HELCOM)
- “LandSeaLot will help define how the land-sea interface can be better observed and how the new observations will be easily integrated as new inputs into our suite of models.” (EDITO Model Lab)
- “The proposal is in line with our mission and, when funded, it will be further discussed and connected to other projects to ensure synergies.” (ENVRI-Board)
- “Interested in any global or regional projects that your proposal might address in inland or coastal waters.” (GeoAqua Watch)
- “Welcome to send us key outcomes of the project and we will try to incorporate as much as possible in our policy and advocacy work.” (World Wildlife Fund)
- “Any monitoring model or service that may strengthen knowledge-based decision-making support could be of interest.” (European Aquaculture Technology & Innovation Platform - EATiP)

HOW: Strategic approach to communications and outreach

Campaigns in support of communication, dissemination and exploitation

In order to ensure a successful delivery of the objectives laid out in Section 2.1, communication and outreach activities will be structured around **four targeted, cross-cutting campaigns**. Each campaign has been conceived with a specific, supporting intention in mind (communicating project activities, and/or exploiting and disseminating

its intermediary and final results), leveraging them to support the project objectives at different stages.

Version 2.0 Update: Specific communication, dissemination, and/or exploitation activities have and are being planned for each campaign, as described in “Example Outputs” below and reflected in the editorial plans presented in Section IV. The results of these activities are being monitored and measured against the targets set for Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), as presented in Section V.

- **CAMPAIGN 1: Promoting for Visibility and Outreach (M1-M48):** This campaign will focus on generating awareness and interest for LandSeaLot amongst key target audiences and related stakeholders (see Table 4), towards building a thriving community around the project.
 - **Version 2.0 Update: Example outputs supporting campaign 1:**
 - Development of LandSeaLot brand and visual identity
 - Introducing LandSeaLot (website and social media launches)
 - Web coverage and multimedia materials (e.g., articles, news items, newsletter items, 9 factsheets, leaflet, infographics) explaining LandSeaLot mission, partners, work packages, and objectives
 - Development of outreach materials (e.g., slide decks, virtual background, templates, etc.)
 - Interviews and profiles of work package leads and partners
 - Targeted media outreach, coverage and press releases announcing the project and its mission
 - LandSeaLot introductory project video

- **CAMPAIGN 2: Documenting and Engaging for Co-Design (M9-M48):** This campaign will focus on conveying stakeholder engagement and activities, promoting and supporting the participation of target audiences and related stakeholders.
 - **Version 2.0 Update: Example outputs supporting campaign 2:**
 - Interviews and profiles of key stakeholders and partners (e.g., low-cost technology developers, community leaders, high-level European representatives)
 - Multimedia materials (e.g. factsheets, leaflets, flyers) developed for target audiences
 - Coverage of stakeholder engagement events (e.g. LandSeaLot Integration Labs stakeholder workshops, General Assemblies, Integration Week, midterm conference, meetings of LandSeaLot Fora)

- Driving and supporting networking and capacity-building opportunities
- Launch of consultations
- Summary and highlights, calls to action
- Engaging social media posts to encourage dialogue with stakeholders
- Promotion of project outcomes and results
- Video documenting and supporting key project activities in WP2-6
- **Version 2.0 Update: CAMPAIGN 3: Amplifying Citizen Engagement for Wider Dissemination and Uptake (M14-48):** This campaign will support, document and create traction towards citizen science activities and training.
 - Example outputs supporting campaign 3:
 - Launch of Citizen Science Hub on project website
 - Launch of LandSeaLot Training Academy Science Hub on project website
 - Multimedia coverage of collaboration, outreach and training activities (e.g. case studies, success stories, video clips)
 - Interviews and profiles of citizen science leaders and community partners
 - Release of catalogues, reports, toolkits and best practices
 - Development of multimedia materials (e.g. factsheets, leaflets, data visualisations, online trainings) to support citizen capacitation and understanding
 - Driving and supporting networking and capacity-building opportunities
 - Promotion of project outcomes and results
 - Targeting and promoting SMEs
 - Video documenting and supporting key project activities in WP2-6 engagement and understanding
- **Version 2.0 Update: CAMPAIGN 4: Transferring Knowledge and Communicating KERs to support Exploitation Targets (M33-48):** This campaign will communicate LandSeaLot's achievement of twelve KERs laid out in the initial Exploitation Plan, and in alignment with five broad Exploitation Targets (Governance and Community of Practices, Best Practices and innovative strategies for observation, Best Practices on data management, and Policy) to support short-term uptake of results as well as long-term impact and sustainability.
 - Example outputs supporting campaign 4:
 - Targeted media outreach, coverage of project achievements

- Communication and dissemination of KERs related to Exploitation Target 1, Government and Community of Practice (e.g. multimedia explanation and coverage of the Common Observation Strategy and its development and effective integration in LandSeaLot Integration Labs, dissemination of gap analysis, online launch and coverage of the Land Sea Lot Citizen Science Hub)
- Communication and Dissemination of KERs related to Exploitation Target 2, Best Practices and Innovation Strategies (e.g. sharing of best practices developed at the LandSeaLot Integration Labs, documentation of improved integrated observation and its impact, support for the development of a toolkit for marinas)
- Communication and Dissemination of KERs related to Exploitation Target 3, Best Practices on Data Management (e.g. multimedia explanation and coverage of interoperability solutions for river, estuarine, citizen science and cost-effective technology data)
- Communication and Dissemination of KERs related to Exploitation Target 4, Market Driven Solutions (e.g. multimedia explanation and promotion of Solutions for Cost-Effective Ocean Observation Platform and portfolio of Earth Observation Products, sharing of data and visualisation tools and services)
- Communication and Dissemination of KERs related to Exploitation Target 5, Policy. This encompasses the communication and dissemination of D7.8 (Policy Brief: Enhancing & Sustaining Observations of the Land-Sea Interface in support of EU GD & the Mission, due M48), including summaries of the policy brief tailored to relevant stakeholder groups.
- LandSeaLot legacy video

Leveraging the Consortium through sound internal communications

While LandSeaLot communication and outreach activities are being coordinated by Work Package 7, participation and close collaboration across all Leads and Work Packages will ensure that the implementation of the COP strategy is well aligned with the overall work plan, towards delivering the LandSeaLot project objectives and deliverables through timely activation of the full Consortium. The following internal communication procedures and tools have been set up towards that end:

- A dedicated LandSeaLot server, hosted by the project coordinator **Deltares**, accessible to all partners, offering document sharing and version control through the Microsoft SharePoint framework.
- Regular Work Package meetings, Steering Committee meetings and annual General Assembly meetings to maximise synergies; minutes and supporting material published on the shared server.
- Brand guidelines, including a project slide deck and recommendations for social media content sharing.

- Internal mailing lists to easily communicate project updates to engaged Consortium partners.
- Best practice editorial processes: iterative draft development, review, fact-checking and approval of material before publication and dissemination.

Leveraging existing networks through effective interactions

LandSeaLot will seek to leverage existing networks to ensure effective interactions with target audiences. Outreach, targeted presentations and/or consultations with key stakeholders will leverage these existing mechanisms, in conjunction with the LandSeaLot Fora. Table 5 lists some of the relevant networks and identifies the LandSeaLot Partner that will be (co)leading interactions.

Table 5. Stakeholder engagement and consultation support networks

Network	Mechanism	LandSeaLot Rep
DANUBIUS-RI	Targeted meetings, workshops and/or interactions (e.g., during General Assembly meetings)	GeoEcoMar
ICOS-ERIC	Targeted meetings, workshops and/or interactions	NORCE
JERICO	Targeted meetings, workshops and/or interactions	Covartec, Deltares, MARIS
EMODnet	Targeted meetings, workshops and/or interactions	SSBE, MARIS
EuroGOOS	Targeted meetings, workshops and/or interactions	HEREON
ENVRI Board	Targeted interactions with the ENVRI Board	Deltares & GeoEcoMar
ENVRI-Hub Comms Group	Meetings of the Communications Group of the ENVRI-Hub project, bringing relevant RI related projects together	SSBE
Mission Ocean Communication Group	Meetings of the Communications Group of the EU Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030”	SSBE
Atlantic & Arctic Lighthouse Weekly Hour	Regular outreach events for topics of relevance to the Atlantic and Arctic Lighthouse	SSBE
Blue Mission BANOS	Regular communications for topics of relevance to the Baltic and North Sea Lighthouse	SSBE

IOC-UNESCO Ocean Best Practice System	Engagement with representatives to present best practices developed during LandSeaLot that can become a reference for wider research communities	MARIS, SMHI
UN Ocean Decade Ocean Data Sharing DCO & OceanPrediction DCC	Engagement with representatives to introduce the aim of LandSeaLot, inform relevant developments, and/or invite input and/or feedback on relevant activities, including by participating in LandSeaLot Co-design Forum	SSBE
EU Citizen Science Platform	Exchanges with the EU Citizen Science Platform for wider outreach and dissemination of relevant citizen science activities (https://eu-citizen.science)	SMHI
EU4Ocean Platform	Leveraging platform activities to give outreach to LandSeaLot, and to connect with wider citizen science networks in Europe	SSBE

WHEN: Timeline for content sharing

Version 2.0 Update: Content on LandSeaLot will be produced and shared throughout the project lifecycle. The frequency of distribution will depend on the type of content produced to support the different phases and campaigns of the strategy. Example communication and dissemination activities in support of Campaigns 1-4 have been outlined above, with the preliminary publication timeline reflected on the editorial calendars included in Section IV of this document.

III: Communication and Outreach Tools, Channels and Materials

Project branding and communication templates

Careful consideration was made to establish the brand identity for LandSeaLot. The key design brief defined a professional aesthetic that feels relative to the aim of integrating land-sea observations, and to reflect European and UK funding.

LandSeaLot logo

Figure 3. LandSeaLot project logo

The LandSeaLot logo was designed to visualise the collaboration towards a **common observation strategy** for the land-sea interface area. The logo references the famous Round Table from the King Arthur legend, of which Arthur and his knights (including the famous knight Lancelot) sat together as equals around a table without a recognisable *head* position. The logo also contains a ‘Fleur-de-Lis’ symbol, with the words Land and Sea left and right of the shape, respectively. At the top of the ‘Fleur-de-Lis’ is the acronym LOT, for the project’s tagline “**Let’s Observe Together**”. The logo was developed during the proposal stage and approved by the project Steering Committee at the project start.

Branding guidelines

The LandSeaLot brand and visual identity was built on the approved logo. Branding Guidelines have been developed specifying the brand’s colours, typography, iconography and templates, for consistent use by the project Consortium when communicating about LandSeaLot (see Figure 4). These guidelines are part of the **Communication Toolkit** which has been made available to the Consortium.

LANDSEALOT BRAND GUIDELINE

Version April 2024

#4080BB #205AA1 #123A81 #F2F2F2 #2762E Gradients

normal version Dark backgrounds

Don't change: design color proportions

ELMODER REGULAR - PRIMARY FONT
LET'S OBSERVE TOGETHER!

Source Sans Pro - secondary font
(used in office templates, reports, presentations)
Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur
1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9

CALL TO ACTION BUTTON

Mind the spelling of the project name:
LandSeaLot (not LANDSEALOT, land-sealot, etc.)

Graphics & icons PPT template & Word templates

Key visual - Fleur-de-lis - connecting observations in the land-sea interface

Co-funded by the European Union UK Research and innovation

EU & UKRI logo and reference to funding and disclaimer needs to be included in all branded material presentations, brochures, or other promotional material.

Figure 4. LandSeaLot branding guidelines

Visual background for virtual meetings

A key visualizer was created as a virtual background (Figure 5) that can be used for Teams or other meeting tools, to promote a strong brand identity through various communication activities.

LET'S OBSERVE TOGETHER!
landsealot.eu

Figure 5. LandSeaLot virtual background

Templates for documents and slide-deck presentations

A user-friendly, MS PowerPoint template has been produced and provided to the Consortium to be used in project communications internally and externally. A MS Word template has also been made available to be used as a template when producing project related Deliverables and/or Milestone reports.

Figure 6. LandSeaLot Microsoft templates

Project website

The LandSeaLot website (www.landsealot.eu) is the primary media channel for project communications. Serving as a comprehensive repository, it contains information on the project including its work plan, partners and team members, as well as hosting tools, reports, articles and blogs, news and events, and reference material for project activities. This online platform is managed by the Work Package 7 team to provide stakeholders with valuable information, resources and updates.

Functioning as a central hub for engagement, the website offers interactive features, such as a newsletter sign-up for regular updates on project progress and related news. Additionally, a user-friendly contact form is available for stakeholders to participate in the “LandSeaLot Co-Designer Forum” and the “LandSeaLot Citizen Science Hub”. Website users can easily contact the LandSeaLot team by clicking the ‘contact us’ button.

Figure 7. Screenshot of the LandSeaLot project website homepage

By prioritising user engagement and accessibility, the LandSeaLot website serves as more than just an information hub, being devised as a dynamic platform designed to foster collaboration, interaction, community building, and meaningful dialogue with stakeholders.

Website enhancement and SEO

When developing the project website, good practices for Search Engine Optimisation (SEO) have been followed to enhance visibility on search engines, such as Google. This includes keyword optimisation, ensuring that relevant keywords are naturally integrated into the content, headings, and meta descriptions. Moreover, meta tags and descriptions are added to all pages, striving for URLs that are clear and descriptive.

The SEO WordPress plugin Yoast has been installed. This plugin helps the website to better perform in search engines like Google. Through a colour coded ranking system the plugin also indicates how content on a webpage can be improved so the ranking of the website increases.

User Experience (UX) Improvements

To create a user-friendly and valuable website experience, effort is placed on various aspects of the site to ensure that users can navigate it effortlessly and find information quickly and intuitively. The commitment to a good user experience includes:

- Streamlined Navigation Menus: Simplifying the structure and organisation of menus to help users find what they need.
- Faster Load Times: Prioritising the speed at which pages load to minimise waiting times and enhance the overall browsing experience.

- **Mobile Responsiveness:** Ensuring that the website performs well across all devices, including desktops, tablets, and smartphones, to provide a consistent experience for all users.
- **Simplified User Interface:** Making the overall interface intuitive and user-friendly, so visitors can interact with the site effectively.

Ultimately, these improvements aim to create a positive and engaging experience for all website visitors, leading to user satisfaction and retention. The LandSeaLot Team will continuously work towards these goals, ensuring that the LandSeaLot website remains a valuable resource for all stakeholders.

Analytics integration

Google Analytics has been integrated into the LandSeaLot website to comprehensively analyse its performance and user interactions, enabling it to track website traffic, monitor user behaviour, and measure engagement metrics. By leveraging these data-driven insights, the Consortium will be able to make informed decisions to optimise website functionality and effectiveness, continuously enhancing the user experience.

All website analytics are consolidated on a customised dashboard and reviewed monthly. The primary metric for evaluating website traffic success is the average number of sessions per month, which will be benchmarked against defined KPI targets (see Section V: Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)).

Social media

LandSeaLot will leverage social media across all the Communication and Outreach campaigns planned to share project updates, promote events, and actively engage with key communities, towards onboarding them in LandSeaLot fora and activities. A thorough analysis of the project landscape, including its 'content territories', (see Figure 8), and the presence and participation of Consortium partners in existing social media channels has been undertaken (see Table 6), to inform the selection of the specific social media channels that will be activated for this purpose and strategic planning of content.

Scoping the social media landscape

Content territories

The LandSeaLot 'content territories' have been scoped and defined to guide the project content strategy across social media channels. This will enable LandSeaLot to strategically reach targeted stakeholder audiences on each social media channel with relevant content, and to support the engagement strategies for the LandSeaLot Project.

Figure 8. LandSeaLot content territories

Presence of Consortium partners in social media

The Consortium partners jointly have a robust and well-established presence on **LinkedIn** (see Table 6). As part of its communication and outreach strategy, LandSeaLot is leveraging this presence to boost the project's impact and rapidly grow a solid follower base within specialised communities by publishing weekly posts on dedicated LinkedIn project channels. By tagging Consortium partners in relevant posts, LandSeaLot messaging will be amplified over a larger audience, therefore increasing the opportunity to engage with more stakeholders. In addition, Partners will be encouraged to like, share, and comment on LandSeaLot social media posts to increase content visibility across their networks, exponentially boosting the dissemination of project activities and results.

Table 6. LinkedIn accounts of LandSeaLot partners and followers (data collected July 2025)

Partner	LinkedIn	Followers (July 2025)
Deltares	linkedin.com/company/deltares/	53,215
Ifremer	linkedin.com/company/ifremer/	95,000
SMHI	linkedin.com/company/smhi/	10,668
MARIS B.V	linkedin.com/company/maris-b-v/	192
SSBE	linkedin.com/company/seascape-belgium	1000
Hereon	linkedin.com/company/hereon-helmholtz/	8489
Covartec	n.a	n.a
GeoEcoMar	n.a	n.a
CNR	linkedin.com/company/consiglio-nazionale-delle-ricerche/	83,000
HCMR	linkedin.com/company/hellenic-centre-for-marine-research/	2,000
NORCE	linkedin.com/company/norce/	25,000
ULiège	linkedin.com/school/university-of-liege/	109,000
TransEurope Marinas	linkedin.com/company/transeurope-marinas/	258
+ATLANTIC	linkedin.com/company/colabatlantic	10,000
ETT S.P.A	linkedin.com/company/ett-spa	9,000

Brockmann Consulting	linkedin.com/company/brockmann-consult/	856
Syke	linkedin.com/company/syke/	24,000
CNRS	linkedin.com/company/cnrs	493,000
University of Stirling	linkedin.com/school/university-of-stirling	88,000
PML	linkedin.com/company/plymouth-marine-laboratory-&-pml-applications-ltd	19,000

LandSeaLot presence on LinkedIn

LinkedIn has been chosen as LandSeaLot’s primary social media platform for outreach and visibility, as it allows for the publication of timely updates and announcements, and a generous 3,000-character limit, which can accommodate posts featuring comprehensive information and storytelling. A direct link to the project account is provided here: [linkedin.com/company/landsealot](https://www.linkedin.com/company/landsealot)

LinkedIn offers various features such as access to professional groups for networking and discussion. Its functionality pushes relevant news and content to specific users based on their profiles. This feature is of special value for the LandSeaLot COP strategy to engage with stakeholders in relevant Fora. As it is widely used for disseminating science, technology and research information, it is useful for monitoring relevant developments in the project landscape. The platform also provides analytics to track the engagement and reach. By maintaining an active presence on LinkedIn, LandSeaLot can actively communicate on its content territories, foster dialogue, gather feedback, and contribute to broader discussions on related topics, thereby enhancing the project visibility across its target audiences and onboarding stakeholder groups on the project activities. The platform is useful as a professional peer-to-peer platform for generating project credibility and positioning, through additional sharing on personal profiles, appealing to potential partners for legacy actions, and effective promotion.

Figure 9. LandSeaLot LinkedIn

LandSeaLot has researched relevant hashtags for its content territories, including in terms of their popularity and reach. A hashtag library has been created (see Table 7) to guide the use of relevant hashtags, following adequate strategies, to optimise engagement and reach the target audiences effectively. LandSeaLot posts will utilise a blend of hashtags, ranging from popular to niche, to maximise impact. For example, popular hashtags e.g. #Water and #DATA provide broader visibility, while niche hashtags offer opportunities to cater to the interests of smaller, more specialised and invested communities. Additionally, LandSeaLot will employ unique brand hashtags e.g. #LandSeaInterface, #LandSeaLot to foster brand recognition and engagement.

Table 7. Relevant hashtags for LandSeaLot LinkedIn communications

Land-Sea Interface	Connecting Research Communities	Ocean and Freshwater Observations	Other Relevant Themes
#Water	#Research	#ClimateChange	#DATA
#Marine	#Collaboration	#ClimateCrisis	#Strategy
#Biodiversity	#Community	#WaterQuality	#Sustainable

#Nature	#Science	#Satellite	#Conservation
#Ocean	#OpenSource	#Ecosystem	#Protection
#Land	#Connect	#Monitoring	#DigitalTwin
#Soil	#Integration	#NatureBasedSolutions	#EU
#Ecosystems	#Volunteer	#MarineBiology	#OneHealth
#Delta	#Networks	#EarthObservation	#EUGreenDeal
#OceanConservation	#Connecting	#Modelling	#BlueEconomy
#habitat	#Cooperation	#MarineConservation	#Habitat
#Interface	#OpenScience	#Algae	#EUFunding
#River	#CitizenScience	#Oceanography	#SciencePolicy
#Coastal	#CoDesign	#NaturalCapital	#Species
#Freshwater	#PublicEngagement	#MarineScience	#OceanLiteracy
#Coast	#Citizen	#EcosystemServices	#EUProject
#Aquatic	#Common	#NBS	#REA
#CoastalManagement	#FAIRData	#Observation	#MissionOcean
#MarineBiodiversity	#InterdisciplinaryResearch	#Freshwater	#EURResearch
#Shoreline	#ResearchCollaboration	#InSitu	#LandSeaLot
#MarineEcosystems	#TeamScience	#OceanHealth	#MappingtheOcean

LandSeaLot presence on X (formerly Twitter)

Version 2.0 Update: The project handle on X is **@LandSea_Lot**.

Figure 10. LandSeaLot X

Version 2.0 Update: LandSeaLot presence on YouTube

YouTube is LandSeaLot’s primary platform for showcasing and archiving videos for media-specific visibility, which are also shared on LinkedIn and the LandSeaLot website. Our channel is: <https://www.youtube.com/@LandSeaLot>.

Figure 11. LandSeaLot YouTube channel

LandSeaLot presence on other social media (e.g. Bluesky)

Version 2.0 Update: Given the relevance of LandSeaLot for stakeholder groups encompassing civil society and citizens, active presence in other social media platforms (i.e. BlueSky) will be considered and activated if timely, relevant and impactful. As a platform with a growing scientific community, we have created a BlueSky account @landsealot.bsky.social to secure the LandSeaLot handle and will continue monitoring partner and stakeholder presence on this platform.

Training workshops, conferences and events

Version 2.0 Update: LandSeaLot's presence at events for 2024-2025 is reflected in Figure 12 below on the following page.

LANDSEALOT AT EVENTS

- Attended **40 events** across Europe
- Engaging with audiences in **15+ countries**
- Reaching **8K+ participants**

Figure 12. LandSeaLot at events

Direct communication and engagement with stakeholders at events provide the LandSeaLot team with the opportunity to raise awareness of the project and to collaborate in support of the project goals. Selected stakeholder groups will also be a key channel harnessed to promote the dissemination and exploitation of the LandSeaLot project results. Table 8 provides an overview of events that have occurred or are being planned to achieve this.

Table 8. LandSeaLot events for the dissemination of KERs

WP	Event type	Description & objectives	Target Audience	When
WP1	Meeting	Session during First General Assembly to introduce and discuss LandSeaLot with key stakeholders	SG1-SG3, SG9	Mar 2024
WP5	LIL workshop	Inaugural Workshop in LIL Baltic Sea (Sweden) - Introducing LandSeaLot and scoping interest for collaboration (13 June)	SG5	Jun 2024
WP5	LIL workshop	Inaugural Workshop in LIL Baltic Sea (Finland) - Introducing LandSeaLot and scoping interest for collaboration (14 June)	SG5	Jun 2024
WP5	LIL workshop	Inaugural Workshop in LIL Seine Estuary and Bay - Introducing LandSeaLot and scoping interest for collaboration (28 June)	SG5	Jun 2024
WP5	LIL workshop	Inaugural Workshop in LIL Po Delta & North Adriatic - Introducing LandSeaLot and scoping interest for collaboration (1 July)	SG5	Jul 2024
WP5	LIL workshop	Inaugural Workshop in LIL Danube Delta - Introducing LandSeaLot and scoping interest for collaboration (12 July)	SG5	Jul 2024
WP5	LIL workshop	Inaugural Workshop in LIL North Aegean - Introducing LandSeaLot and scoping interest for collaboration (18 July)	SG5	Jul 2024
WP5	LIL workshop	Inaugural Workshop in LIL Wadden Sea Rhine Elbe (Germany) - Introducing LandSeaLot and scoping interest for collaboration	SG5	Jun 2024
WP5	LIL workshop	Inaugural Workshop in LIL Wadden Sea Rhine Elbe (Netherlands) - Introducing LandSeaLot and scoping interest for collaboration	SG5	Jul 2024
WP5	LIL workshop	Second Workshop in LIL Wadden Sea Rhine Elbe (Germany) - Introducing LandSeaLot and scoping interest for collaboration	SG5	August 2024

WP5	LIL workshop	Inaugural Workshop in LIL Tagus & Sado Estuaries - Introducing LandSeaLot and scoping interest for collaboration	SG5	Sep 2024
WP5	LIL workshop	Inaugural Workshop in LIL Firth of Forth - Introducing LandSeaLot and scoping interest for collaboration	SG5	Planned for Jun-Sep 2024
WP5	LIL workshop	Inaugural Workshop in LIL Gulf of Lions - Introducing LandSeaLot and scoping interest for collaboration	SG5	Planned for Jun-Sep 2024
All WPs	LSL Integration Week	LandSeaLot Week #1 organised to connect communities, discuss common approaches & advance collaboration	All SGs	Jan 2025
WP2	LSL Integration Week - workshop	First Integration Workshop with LSC & LCD: Co-designing and aligning a common vision for observing the land-sea interface	SG1-3, SG8-11	Jan 2025
WP2	LSL Integration Week - workshop	RI Community Workshop during the First LandSeaLot Integration Week	SG1-3, SG9	Jan 2025
WP5	LIL Workshop	Workshop in LIL Wadden Sea Rhine Elbe	SG5	March 2025
WP5	LIL Workshop	Workshop on the Tagus and Sado LIL with governance institutions, state laboratories, academia, and NGOs.	SG5	May 2025
WP5	LIL Workshop	Workshop Tagus and Sado LIL with Blue Schools	SG5	May 2025
WP2	LSL workshop	Online workshop held to present, discuss and consolidate the commonalities and potential divergences in existing communities' strategies (RIs, satellite, modelling)	SG1-3, SG9	Sep 2025
WP2	LSL workshop	2nd Integration Workshop with LSC & LCD workshop to foster networking between the communities' representatives towards drafting the LCOS as well as joint services	SG1-3, SG8-11	Dec 2025
All WPs	LSL Integration week	LandSeaLot Week #2 organised to connect communities, discuss common approaches & advance collaboration	All SGs	March 2026
WP2	LSL Integration week - workshop	RI/EO community Workshop during the 2nd LandSeaLot Integration Week	SG1-3, SG9	March 2026
WP7	LSL Conference	LandSeaLot Mid-term Conference	All SGs	Sept 2026

WP4, (WP3, WP5, WP6)	LSL workshop	Workshop ensuring integration of observation strategy (WP3), low-cost technologies (WP4) and data management (WP6)	SG1	Jul 2026
WP2	LSL workshop	Workshop with LSC and LCD: Identify and co-design joint services at the land-sea interface area	SG1-3, SG8-11	Dec 2026
All WPs	LSL Integration week	LandSeaLot Week #3 organised to connect communities, discuss common approaches and advance collaboration	All SGs	Jan 2027
WP2	LSL Integration week - workshop	RI, EO/Modelling Community Workshop during the 3rd LandSeaLot Integration Week	SG1-3, SG9	Jan 2027
WP4, (WP3, WP5, WP6)	LSL workshop	Workshop ensuring integration of observation strategy (WP3), low-cost technologies (WP4) and data management (WP6)	SG1	Jul 2027
WP2	LSL workshop	Workshop with LSC and LCD: Develop a consolidated version of LCOS	SG1-3, SG8-11	Jul 2027
All WPs	LSL Integration week	LandSeaLot Integration Week #4 organised to connect communities, discuss common approaches and advance collaboration	All SGs	Jan 2028
WP7	LSL conference	Final conference to convey the project outcomes to all SGs, inviting further establishment of synergies, exploitation and capitalisation of results and summarising key science-to-policy recommendations to SG8, SG9 and SG10	All SGs	Jan 2028

Adding to these, Consortium Partners will seek to give outreach to LandSeaLot activities, progress and results through participation in relevant (3rd party) conferences, events, and meetings. An “Event Log” has been produced to keep track of the aggregate presence and impact achieved through these efforts.

Version 2.0 Update: Table 9 below is an updated list of key conferences and events that have been or will be targeted for promotion of LandSeaLot in 2024-2025. Opportunities will be continuously scoped and recorded for 2026 on.

Table 9. Key events in 2024-2025 to support LandSeaLot awareness

Name	Description	When
European Maritime Day 2024	The European Maritime Day (EMD) is an annual 2-day event where Europe’s maritime community meet to network, discuss, and outline joint action on maritime affairs and the blue economy.	May 2024

International Liege Colloquium on Ocean Dynamics 2024	The International Liège Colloquium focused on Ocean Extremes with contributions encompassing observational and modelling studies, research on the evolution of extreme events over the last decades and their projected evolution in the future.	May 2024
Science is Wonderful	A science fair organised by the EU Commission to inspire European Youth to get involved in science. Various Horizon EU projects had booths presenting their methodology and findings.	Apr 2024
Doors Stakeholder Conference: Black Sea Futures: Science, Prosperity and People	Conference highlighting Black Sea research and innovation including advancements in the Digital Twin Ocean concept, capacity building in the Black Sea region, Ocean Literacy, and the intersection of science and policy.	Apr 2024
JERICO-RI General Assembly	Final General Assembly presenting achievements of the JERICO-S3 project and discussions about the future of the JERICO-RI European Infrastructure.	Jun 2024
Digital Ocean Forum (DOF) 2024	The DOF is an annual event bringing together research projects and initiatives contributing to co-create the European DTO.	Jun 2024
FAIR Data on Biochemistry in European Waters	The “FAIR Data on Biochemistry in European Waters: Current Status and Way Forward Webinar” is geared at supporting data collection initiatives in organising FAIR data flows, e.g., for enhanced modelling or digital twinning purposes.	Jul 2024
AMEMR 2024	The Marine Ecosystem Modelling Research Conference (AMEMR) promotes interdisciplinary discussions among stakeholders and modelling, observational and experimental scientists.	Jul 2024
PECS Conference 2024	The Physics of Estuaries and Coastal Seas (PECS) Conference is where experts meet to promote and exchange information on recent developments in physics of estuaries and coastal seas.	Sep 2024
ICOS Science Conference 2024	One of the themes in ICOS Science Conference 2024 is dedicated to Carbon Cycling along the Land Ocean Aquatic Continuum.	Sep 2024
European Researchers Night 2024	LandSeaLot Poster at EU Researchers Night in Bucharest.	Sep 2024
Ocean Optics XXVI	This event brings together a diverse ocean optics community, including oceanographers, optical engineers, Earth observation scientists, and policy professionals from across the globe.	Oct 2024
DANUBIUS-RI Modelling Node	DANUBIUS-RI Modelling Node: Workshop on Coastal Ecological Modelling (29 Oct)	Oct 2024
Ocean Week	Ocean Week puts together debates, exhibitions, and other events to celebrate Europe’s seas; the event focuses on ocean literacy.	Oct 2024
Eutrophication Expert Group of OSPAR	Group of eutrophication experts and national representatives to prepare reporting and measures on eutrophication for OSPAR.	Jan 2025

9th EMB Forum: Addressing Coastal and Water Resilience in the Land Sea Interface	This one-day event explored different aspects at the land-sea interface, including policy and governance, transboundary pollution, and coastal adaptation and liveability.	Feb 2025
CoastPredict GA 2025	Presenting LandSeaLots approach to increasing the number of <i>in situ</i> observations at the land-sea interface through the use of cost-effective sensors and citizen science.	Feb 2025
Ocean Innovation Africa	Presenting LandSeaLots approach to increasing the number of <i>in situ</i> observations at the land-sea interface through the use of cost-effective sensors and citizen science.	Feb 2025
EU Ocean Days 2025	Present at the Ocean Literacy Islands as members of EU4Ocean.	Mar 2025
OpenSeaLab 4.0 Hackathon	This event brings together data and multidisciplinary scientists, software developers, social innovators, students, and businesses to harness the open-source, marine data offered by EMODnet to develop solutions to Ocean challenges.	Mar 2025
MARTECH 2025	Flash talk on smart Bays & international observing initiatives enhanced by Marine Technology.	May 2025
THE OCEAN RACE EUROPE 2025 -IMOCA	The starting point for a major sailing race will be in Brest, France featuring citizen science activity concerning sensors on some competing yachts. LandSeaLot will be present in various locations presenting the work being done to increase observation capacity in the LSI.	May 2025
EMD 2025	LandSeaLot colleagues were present to network with other members of the EU maritime community and discuss joint action.	May 2025
EGU 2025	A poster was presented at the European Geoscience Union General Assembly detailing LandSeaLot's work with cost-effective sensors for ocean observation.	May 2025
UNOC 2025	Surfer Scientists Workshop. Testing dedicated GPS and water temperature sensors on paddle boards to demonstrate the potential of cost-effective technology and citizen-scientist collaborations	June 2025
European Digital Ocean Pavilion - UNOC 2025	Coastal Challenges Session - how LandSeaLot is responding to observation challenges by testing and deploying cost-effective observation technology and building capacity among local communities to observe and study the land-sea interface.	June 2025
ESA Living Planet Symposium 2025	Earth Observation conference, which in 2025 will centre around the intensifying climate crisis, with an emphasis in transitioning from 'observation to climate action and sustainability for Earth'.	Jun 2025
Digital Ocean Forum (DOF) 2025	The DOF is an annual event bringing together research projects and initiatives contributing to co-create the European DTO.	Jun 2025

Marine Heat Waves from Space: from Detection to Prediction Workshop	The Tagus and Sado Estuaries System LandSeaLot Integration Lab will share insights on their work monitoring heatwaves during this workshop.	Oct 2025
SedNet 2025	LandSeaLot will participate in discussions about the different challenges related to the theme of the conference: “Healthy Sediments”.	Oct 2025
EMODnet Conference	This conference will showcase the latest innovations in EMODnet’s marine <i>in situ</i> data services and infrastructure upgrades towards the European Digital Twin Ocean.	Nov 2025

Newsletter, press releases and direct mail

Version 2.0 Update: The LandSeaLot Observer (see Figure 13) was launched in September 2024 and is used to convey key ongoing project developments. It is distributed **quarterly** via a GDPR compliant tool. Recipients will have subscribed to the newsletter from the website via a registration form or will have been invited to subscribe to the newsletter after following LandSeaLot on LinkedIn.

Titled “The LandSeaLot Observer”, the newsletter typically features the following sections. It remains open to adjustment.

- LandSeaLot project logo and information.
- Section One, Welcome Note: Brief personal hello from work package leaders, drawing attention to project highlights and newsletter themes.
- Section Two, New Visions: A section announcing new project video outputs, when relevant.
- Section Three, LIL Spotlight: A short feature on the activities and aims of one of the nine LandSeaLot Integration Labs.
- Section Four, LandSeaLot Stories: A roundup of articles published on the LandSeaLot website over the last quarter.
- Section Five, Outreach & Activities: A roundup of Consortium activities and presence at events over the past quarter.
- Section Six, Events: Information about relevant upcoming events.
- Section Seven, Sandstones: A light-hearted signoff featuring games, pictures, jokes, etc.
- Boilerplate footer: Funding statement, call to action for website, social media sign-ups, etc.

Figure 13. The LandSeaLot newsletter

Besides the quarterly newsletter, **press releases** will be sent out to relevant media outlets and contacts to give outreach to project results. Potential media outlets and contacts include:

Science news outlets

- Nature (contact: news@nature.com)
- Science (contact: news@aaas.org)
- New Scientist (contact: news@newscientist.com)
- Science News (contact: editors@sciencenews.org)
- <https://www.sciencemediacentre.org/>

Environmental news outlets

- Environmental News Network (contact: editor@enn.com)
- The Guardian - Environment (contact: environment@theguardian.com)
- Yale Environment 360 (contact: info@e360.yale.edu)

Ocean and marine science news outlets

- Oceanographic (contact: contact@oceanographicmagazine.com)
- Marine Science Today (contact: info@marinesciencetoday.com)
- Ocean News and Technology (contact: info@oceannews.com)

General news outlets

- BBC News (contact: news.online@bbc.co.uk)
- CNN (contact: newsdesk@CNN.com)
- Reuters (contact: news@thomsonreuters.com)

Local outlets will be targeted when giving outreach to planned meetings and events, leveraging the contacts and relations of Project Partners with their local networks.

Scientific publications and posters

The LandSeaLot Consortium will seek to disseminate the results of the project via peer-reviewed scientific publications, project reports, and oral and poster presentations at national, European and international conferences. At least one scientific publication will be produced by the end of the project (Deltares), outlining the key results of the project.

Version 2.0 Update: A Zenodo Community has been created for LandSeaLot. Zenodo is an open-access digital repository, allowing researchers to share project-related research and outputs including data sets, software, presentations and posters in compliance with Open Science and FAIR principles.

The LandSeaLot Community handle is <https://zenodo.org/communities/landsealot>. All Consortium members can join and upload project outputs to this space. WP7 will circulate detailed Zenodo instructions to all Consortium members in 2025.

Other supporting communication and outreach resources and materials

The following materials have been developed or are planned for production and will be available to further support the implementation of the LandSeaLot COP.

Infographics and flyers

A general infographic has been developed as a user-friendly device to communicate the main objectives of the project and key messaging. Printed copies of the infographic (500 units) have been produced for distribution at key conferences, events and meetings. Further visual communications and infographics will be produced throughout the project, to support outreach and engagement of target audiences.

LandSeaLot seeks to **integrate, scale-up and enhance existing observation efforts** – including *in-situ*, satellite, modelling and citizen science – to better study the **land-sea interface**.

Figure 14. General LandSeaLot infographic

A second infographic was created to represent the Integration Labs. This visual is used in communications related to the **LandSeaLot Integration Labs**.

INTEGRATION LABS

Figure 15. LandSeaLot Integration Labs infographic

Version 2.0 Update: Factsheets

Nine factsheets have been produced and published profiling each of the LandSeaLot Integration Labs (LILs) and intended to support communication and outreach activities undertaken by the LILs. Each factsheet describes the physical setting relevant to each LIL and details the environmental and societal challenges they are working to address, supported by illustrative graphics. The factsheets also convey LandSeaLot’s overall mission and demonstrate the connection between LILs and local communities. The factsheets are available in digital form on the project website. A physical leaflet containing a QR code linking to the factsheets online was also produced to support in-person communication and outreach. The second page of the leaflet provides a link to the first LandSeaLot project video.

Figure 16. LandSeaLot Integration Labs factsheets

Version 2.0 Update: Project video

A 4-minute video, “Introducing LandSeaLot: Let’s Observe Together” was produced to introduce and promote project ambitions, objectives and planned activities. It was released at the first LandSeaLot Integration Week (January 2025) and published on the project’s YouTube channel, website and LinkedIn.

Figure 17. Screenshots from LandSeaLot project video

Version 2.0 Update: Ad hoc videos

1–2-minute videos will continue to be produced on an ad hoc basis to enhance storytelling and increase impact. These will be available on the project website and YouTube channel and will be publicised on social media.

Figure 18. Screenshots from low-cost sensor video

Legacy video

The key results and outcomes of the project will be further captured and promoted through a video which will be ready by the project end, for legacy.

Project slide deck

A general project presentation has been produced for consortium partners to give an overview of the project at conferences, events and meetings. This slide deck offers a comprehensive overview of the project and its goals.

Figure 19. LandSeaLot slide deck

Posters

Two posters have been created to present the project in national, European, and international events, namely, 1) a general LandSeaLot poster, and 2) a second poster with a more specific focus on the project activities and fora. These posters will be further updated and/or customised to support outreach and dissemination activities, as appropriate.

Figure 20. Left: LandSeaLot general poster. Right: LandSeaLot pillar poster

Roll-up banner

A general roll-up banner has been designed to support branding at meetings and events.

**LET'S
OBSERVE
TOGETHER!**

LandSeaLot seeks to integrate and enhance existing observation efforts - including *in-situ*, satellite, modelling and citizen science - to better study the land-sea interface, where terrestrial and marine habitats meet.

LANDSEALOT.EU

Figure 21. LandSeaLot roll-up banner

Sticker

A sticker with the LandSeaLot logo, website link and social media handle/hashtag was produced and distributed to the consortium partners at the annual meeting, and at subsequent meetings and events.

Figure 22. LandSeaLot sticker

Flyers

A general print-friendly LandSeaLot flyer (Figure 23) was designed and will be used for outreach to early students and members of the public interested in learning about the citizen science activities planned throughout the project.

Figure 23. LandSeaLot general flyer

A specific flyer was designed to promote LandSeaLot amongst providers of cost-effective technologies, towards scoping available solutions to support citizen scientists seeking to engage in observing the land-sea interface area.

LANDSEALOT IS LOOKING TO BUY YOUR COST-EFFECTIVE MARINE TECHNOLOGY!
APPLY BY 15 JULY 2024!

We aim to procure € 250 000 of cost-effective marine technologies to scale solutions that meet ocean management and decision-making needs.

Monitoring our oceans by moving beyond technical specifications, and prioritising the practicalities of data collection, analysis, and dissemination is a timely necessity. The LandSeaLot project (landsealot.eu), funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme for Research and Innovation under grant agreement No.101134575, is rising to the challenge by establishing a cost-effective technology procurement and evaluation procedure. This initiative is focused on demonstrating the capabilities of devices and early commercial products in specific sites known as the LandSeaLot Integration Labs. These sites will be equipped with technical solutions to collect new *in situ* observations and, thereby addressing observation gaps in the land-sea interface.

What is cost-effective technology?

- Technology with substantially lower costs than referenced, conventionally used products with the same or similar functionality
- Tools, devices or systems designed, developed and priced to be affordable and accessible to a wide range of users

What is the evaluation process?

The project is expected to allocate approximately € 250 000 for technology procurement, distributed among several technologies. To propose your technology for consideration, please complete our intake spreadsheet and follow the submission instructions on the second page. Once received, the information will be evaluated, assessing impact, feasibility and performance against manufacturer specifications. Our evaluations will involve consultations among experts and users, with an emphasis on the product-market fit. Technologies determined as suitable for LandSeaLot's purposes will be considered for purchase, following a transparent procurement process.

What are the technologies considered?

- Platforms, sensors, and samplers
- Ongoing recurrent costs for use, such as maintenance, calibration and work needed to produce useful data
- Technology ready in the volumes quoted at the outset, or ready for manufacturing, pending LandSeaLot's procurement
- Innovations targeting all fields: physics, biogeochemistry, chemistry, biology
- All stages of readiness levels, however priority will be given to technology with readiness levels from Technology Validated in Lab (TRL 4) to Actual System Proven in Operational Environment (TRL 9), but not yet in broad use

HOW TO SUBMIT YOUR INFORMATION?
 Complete the spreadsheet template available at landsealot.eu/submission and send it to: landsealot@smhi.se by 15 July 2024. Attach a photo of the device to your email and feel free to add any relevant documents.

SUBMIT YOUR FORM TODAY!

The spreadsheet template includes the following points to address:

Organisation details:

- Company or organisation name, website, social medias
- Point of contact name, email address, phone number

Costs (Euros):

- Unit cost options, volume discount if any
- Peripheral/ accessory cost options
- Training cost options

Basic technology specifications:

- Device name, model, version, dimensions, weight
- Variables/parameters measured, expected performance/accuracy and measuring range for each parameter, frequency of measurements
- Technology readiness level
- Expected sensor/lifetime, power supply type, battery lifetime if applicable
- Data transmission tools and frequency, format, memory capacity
- Environmental friendliness of the materials used
- Description of the intended use(s)

Information on the data flow

Practicality:

- Manufacturer name, website, social medias
- Estimated lead time to delivery
- Production level

For additional questions, please contact us at landsealot@smhi.se.

LET'S OBSERVE TOGETHER!

Co-funded by the European Union and UK Research and Innovation

LandSeaLot has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme for Research and Innovation under grant agreement No. 101134575. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Council Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. EU participants in Horizon Europe Project LandSeaLot are supported by UMH grant numbers: 3020562 University of Stirling and 3020758 Plymouth Marine Laboratory.

Figure 24. LandSeaLot cost-effective technology tender flyer

Version 2.0 Update: A LandSeaLot Integration Labs flyer was produced to amplify awareness of the work of the LILs and direct target audiences toward the nine factsheets (see Figure 19) detailing the aims and activities of each LIL.

Discover the LandSeaLot Integration Labs

LandSeaLot Integration Labs are dynamic testing sites for developing and refining a Common Observation Strategy across land-sea interface areas in Europe. They serve as centres to test new methods and technologies, following a community-based approach to advance the observation of river mouths, estuaries and deltas.

landsealot.eu/factsheets

The flyer features a central map of Europe with nine integration lab locations highlighted in colored segments:

- SEINE ESTUARY AND BAY
- FIRTH OF FORTH
- WADDEN SEA, RHINE DELTA AND ELBE ESTUARY
- BALTIC SEA
- DANUBE DELTA AND COASTAL AREA
- NORTH AEGEAN
- PO DELTA AND NORTH ADRIATIC
- GULF OF LIONS AND RHONE DELTA
- TAGUS AND SADO ESTUARIES SYSTEM

Figure 25. LandSeaLot Integration Labs Flyer

IV: Planning of communications and outreach Activities

Version 2.0 Update: The LandSeaLot Communication and Outreach strategy is being implemented through an Editorial Action Plan. This has been produced as a living document that is updated regularly, to bring relevant developments into consideration and adapt planned measures accordingly.

The Editorial Action Plan takes the form of a calendar representing project activities, editorial channels and outputs, and events over M1-24 of the project. It simultaneously maps:

- C&D Campaigns
- Quarterly newsletters
- Monthly articles
- News items (ad hoc)
- Weekly LinkedIn posts
- Project events
- External relevant events

This is a living document that is updated on a weekly basis. Items in green tones have been published, items in orange tones are in progress, and items in red tones are planned and subject to change.

Communication and outreach activities (Month 19-48)

Year	2026												2027												2028						
Month #	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	
Month	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	
Campaign	Campaign 1: Promoting for Visibility & Outreach				Campaign 2: Documenting and Engaging for Co-Design				Campaign 1: Promoting for Visibility & Outreach (M1-A445)				Campaign 2: Documenting and Engaging for Co-Design				Campaign 1: Promoting for Visibility & Outreach				Campaign 2: Documenting and Engaging for Co-Design				Campaign 1: Promoting for Visibility & Outreach						
Deliverables, Milestones, Tasks	sign				Campaign 3: Amplifying Citizen Engagement for Wider Dissemination & Uptake				Campaign 3: Amplifying Citizen Engagement for Wider Dissemination & Uptake				Campaign 4: Transferring Knowledge and Communicating KERs to support Exploitation Targets				Campaign 3: Amplifying Citizen Engagement for Wider Dissemination & Uptake				Campaign 4: Transferring Knowledge and Communicating KERs to support Exploitation Targets										
Newsletters (Quarterly)		Newsletter 5 - a summer of landsalot			Newsletter 6				Newsletter 7				Newsletter 8				Newsletter 9		Newsletter 10				Newsletter 11			Newsletter 12			Newsletter 13		Newsletter 14
Articles (Monthly)	Initial design - salt vision (Po LIL)	LIL Spotlight 4 North Aegean	Stakeholder spotlight: the Ocean Race	Citizen Science in the North Aegean	LIL Spotlight 5: Forth of Forth	Year in review	Societal challenges: carbon fluxes	LIL Spotlight 6	Integration Week 2 Recap	Societal challenge: flooding	Citizen science success story (TBO)	LIL Spotlight 7: bid	Societal challenge: heatwaves	Citizen science success story (TBO)	Societal challenge: morphological change/coastal erosion	LIL Spotlight 8 (final)	Citizen science success story (TBO)	Societal challenge: biodiversity	Stakeholder engagement story (TBO)	Societal challenge: nutrients	LIL Spotlights: Interview with WPS	KER story: data management in LandSeaLot	KER: Earth Observation in the Spotlight (related to portfolio of EO products)	Case study: the value of integrated observation	Stakeholder engagement story (TBO)	KER story: data management in LandSeaLot	KER story: LandSeaLot's market-driven solutions	KER story: the importance of interoperability (for citizen science, river estuarine data, and lowest cost sensor data)	Community Forum: project successes	Common Observation Strategy coverage	
News (Adhoc)							Integration Week Announcements 2	Integration Week				Midterm Conference Announcements	Midterm conference																		
Social Media W1																															
Social Media W2																															
Social Media W3																															
Social Media W4		Newsletter 5																													
Social Media W5																															
Events (LSL)		LIL online workshop (SG1-3, 9) to discuss existing community strategies (RIs, satellite, modelling) (WP2)	Marine Heatwaves workshop - email invite 2025, list asked who could attend	EMODnet Conference	Workshop from community reps towards drafting the LCOS (SG1-3, 9-11) (WP2)		LSL Integration Week 2 and workshops (WP2)	LSL Conference (all stakeholders) (WP2)		Workshop (all stakeholders) ensuring integration of observation strategy (WP3), low-cost tech (WP4) and data management (WP6)						Workshop with LSC and LCD: identify and co-design services at the land-sea interface (SG1-3, 11, WP2)	LSL Integration Week 3 (all SGs) (WP2)						Workshop for integration of observation strategy (WP3), low-cost technologies (WP4) and data management (WP6) (SG1) (WP4) and Workshop with LSC and LCD to deliver LCOS (SG1-3, 9-11) (WP2)						Integration week (All WPs) and final LSL Conference (WP2)		
Events (Third Party)																															
Events (Marine Context)																															

Figure 27. Communication and outreach editorial overview (M19-M18)

V: Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Version 2.0 Update: These KPIs have been updated as of June 2025 and remain subject to change. Partners may propose revisions to the KPIs with justification as plans evolve.

Table 10. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and targets for monitoring progress of the LandSeaLot COP

KPI No.	Campaign	Relevant KER(s)	Action type	Measures	Target 2025	Target 2028	Status July 2025
1	Campaign 1: Promoting for Visibility and Outreach		Project branding	Branding for consistent project visual identity and messaging	1 kit	1 kit	1 kit complete
2	Campaign 1: Promoting for Visibility and Outreach		Project branding	LandSeaLot printed infographic (distribution)	500	1,500	500 ongoing on track
3	Campaign 1: Promoting for Visibility and Outreach		Project branding	Roll-up banners	2	2	2 complete
4	Campaign 1: Promoting for Visibility and Outreach		Project branding	Posters	3	5	2 ongoing on track (3 planned by end of 2025)
5	Campaign 1: Promoting for Visibility and Outreach		Project public website	Average sessions per month	>0.5k	>1.5k	1,004 ongoing on track
6	Campaign 1: Promoting for Visibility and Outreach		Social media	Followers across all platforms	>250	>500	648 complete
7	Campaign 1: Promoting for Visibility and Outreach		Newsletters	Newsletters published	6	14	4 ongoing on track (6 planned by end of 2025)
8	Campaign 1: Promoting for		Press Releases	Press releases	1	5	3 ongoing

	Visibility and Outreach						<u>on track</u>
9	Campaign 1: Promoting for Visibility and Outreach		LandSeaLot promotional video	Number of views	>150	>300	1,213 complete
10	Campaign 1: Promoting for Visibility and Outreach		Pay-per click (PPC) campaigns	Overall views of project videos	500	>1000	complete Video view targets have been achieved. PPC to be evaluated and used if needed throughout the project.
11	Campaign 1: Promoting for Visibility and Outreach		Project branding	Infographic #1 (LandSeaLot Observing Communities)	400 distributed 300 downloads	2000 printed and online downloads	400 printed 125 distributed 308 downloads ongoing, downloads on track, will be distributed at 2025 events to reach target
12	Campaign 2: Engagement for Co-design		Fostering awareness on Integration Labs	9 Factsheets (Integration Labs)	450 distributed 500 downloads		119 downloads ongoing below target; further social media promotion to come
13	Campaign 2: Engagement for Co-design		Advocacy and literacy about the land-sea interface	Infographic #2 (Climate Change Threats)	200 distributed. 200 downloads		pending, due M42

14	Campaign 2: Engagement for Co-design		Advocacy and literacy about the land-sea interface	Infographic #3 (Preserving Biodiversity)	200 distributed, 200 downloads		pending, due M42
15	Campaign 2: Engagement for Co-design		Advocacy and literacy about the land-sea interface	Infographic #4 (Reducing Pollution from Land)	200 distributed, 200 downloads		pending, due M42
16	Campaign 2: Onboarding for Co-Design	KER 1.1 – LCOS & Agreements by parties KER 5.1 - Policy Briefs	Online survey to gather stakeholder feedback and input towards LandSeaLot vision and policy recommendations	Number of responses to survey	n.a	>50	pending, due M42
17	Campaign 3: Training for Wider Dissemination and Uptake	KER 1.3 – Citizen Science Hub	Training materials for citizen scientists	Number of downloads	>100	>200	0 pending below target; Training Academy launch (Milestone 11) due in July 2025
18	Campaign 1: Visibility and Outreach	KER 1.3 – Citizen Science Hub	Outreach Webinars	Avg. # participants per webinar organised	30	30	pending below target; no webinars held so far. Note: target remains the same regardless of total number of webinars. Webinars may be organised by the Training Academy

19	Campaign 1: Visibility and Outreach		Multimedia content	Short clips available	1	>5	2 ongoing on track
20	Campaign 2: Onboarding for Co-Design		Networking	External stakeholder representatives engaged during “LSL Weeks” 1, 2, 3	>25	>50	22 ongoing below target
21	Campaign 2: Onboarding for Co-Design		Community workshops in LandSeaLot Integration Labs	Average # Community Workshops per LandSeaLot Integration Labs	4	8	1.5 average workshop per LIL ongoing - in addition to workshops, stakeholder engagement activities such as sensor demonstrations, online meetings, and community outreach indicate that LILs are on target to engage a wide range of stakeholders.
22	Campaign 2: Onboarding for Co-Design		Midterm conference	Participants	n.a	>70	pending, due M32
23	Campaign 3: Amplifying Citizen Engagement for Wider Dissemination	KER 1.3 – Citizen Science Hub	Training-the-Trainers Academy	Participants trained	n.a	>50	pending
24	Campaign 3: Amplifying Citizen Engagement for Wider Dissemination		Networking	SMEs engaged	n.a	>15	27 complete
25	Campaign 4: Transferring	KER 2.3 – Toolkit for	LandSeaLot Citizen	# of marinas receiving the	+25	+50	pending

	Knowledge for Exploitation & Sustainability	deployment of citizen science via European marinas	Science Toolkit (tips and resources for marinas)	Citizen Science Toolkit			below target; KPI more likely to be met within 2026.
25	Campaign 4: Transferring Knowledge for Exploitation & Sustainability		LandSeaLot legacy video	Views	n.a	>1000	pending, due M48
27	Campaign 4: Transferring Knowledge for Exploitation & Sustainability		Participation to 3rd party events	# of persons to which LSL presentations have been exposed	+750	+2000	8,679 ongoing on track
28	Campaign 4: Transferring Knowledge for Exploitation & Sustainability		Final Conference	Participants	n.a	>70	pending, due M48
29	Campaign 4: Transferring Knowledge for Exploitation & Sustainability	KER 1.1 – LCOS & Agreements by parties	LCOS and Exploitation Plan	Pledge and/or MoU and/or SLAs established	+1	+1	1 ongoing on track
30	Campaign 4: Transferring Knowledge for Exploitation & Sustainability	KER 5.1 - Policy Briefs	Policy brief	Policy briefs distributed	n/a	+150	pending, due M42

VI: External opportunities and tools to maximise impact

Opportunities provided or facilitated by the European Commission to optimise dissemination and exploitation of LandSeaLot results will be explored. These include:

- [EU Research and Innovation](#)
- [Horizon Magazine](#)
- [Horizon Results Booster](#)
- [Open Research Europe](#)

Project synergies

LandSeaLot partners are actively engaged in a range of other relevant projects and activities. Wherever possible and beneficial, LandSeaLot communications and outreach activities will be developed and implemented in collaboration with other initiatives to maximise impacts and synergies with existing resources.

VII: Post-Project Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation

The LandSeaLot website will remain live and accessible after the project's end to enable continued dissemination and exploitation of key exploitable results and project information, including the archive of blogs, newsletters, videos, training materials, and policy briefs. The website will remain online at least until all directly project-related communication, dissemination and exploitation activities by the project have been completed, and for a minimum of four years after the project ends in line with obligations detailed in the project's Grant Agreement.

Key events and conferences will be identified to disseminate project results in the immediate year following the completion of the project and partners will be identified to disseminate LandSeaLot results going forward – to ensure the sustainability and further multiplication of the project outputs beyond the project period.

The [Zenodo Community](#) will remain active and accessible after project completion, with Consortium researchers able to share project-related research and outputs including data sets, software, presentations and posters in compliance with Open Science and FAIR principles. Zenodo will serve as the lasting repository for public deliverables and other LandSeaLot outputs, ensuring they remain accessible following the project's end.

The **LandSeaLot legacy video**, published in M48, will give a succinct and lasting summary of the project's achievements, communicate project KERs, and support long-term impact and legacy.

Planned communication, dissemination and exploitation activities beyond the project's end will be updated and revised as needed, and will be informed by the ongoing work of Task 7.4, (Building paths towards exploitation and legacy, including policy foresight and recommendations, M1-M48) and Task 2.5 (LandSeaLot legacy report due M48).

VIII: Conclusion

This document has outlined the updated Communication and Outreach Plan (COP2.0) for the LandSeaLot project, delivered as D7.2 in M18 (July 2025). The plan will continue to be updated regularly and revised internally throughout the remaining project lifetime.

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